

Bridging the Middle-Income Trap: The Snowball Effect of Economic Development during Jokowi's Leadership

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Abstract. Indonesia, endowed with substantial natural resources and a strategic archipelagic position, holds significant potential for economic advancement. However, since 2000, the country's economic growth has been inconsistent, posing a challenge to the developmental objectives of President Jokowi's administration, which began in 2014. Despite various policy efforts, Indonesia remains trapped in the middle-income bracket. Through in-depth qualitative analysis, this study aims to critically assess the measures that have been implemented and the effectiveness of Jokowi's economic policies in addressing the structural challenges that have impeded Indonesia's progress. This research is grounded in a liberal interventionist perspective, which advocates for active government involvement in the economy to safeguard and enhance capitalist structures, by particularly focusing on the industrial policies enacted in Jokowi's administration. By examining the interplay between state intervention and market forces, the research endeavors to shed light on the potential pathways for Indonesia to overcome the middle-income trap. Contributing to the broader discourse on economic development, this research is anticipated to guide Indonesia in its quest to overcome the middle-income trap, laying the foundation for sustained economic growth and long-term national prosperity..

KEYWORDS

1. Economic Development.
2. Indonesia's Growth Strategy.
3. Industrial Policy.
4. Jokowi's Leadership.
5. MIT.

1. Introduction

Background

Indonesia stands at a critical juncture, a nation brimming with economic promise yet grappling with significant hurdles. With its rich natural resources, strategic geographic position, and a large, youthful population, Indonesia holds vast economic potential. However, it remains categorized as a middle-income country, facing the daunting challenge of the middle-income trap (MIT). This phenomenon, where nations find themselves unable to sustain the rapid growth

needed to achieve high-income status, poses a formidable obstacle to Indonesia's aspirations. Countries caught within this trap often experience a slowdown in productivity and innovation, resulting in economic inertia. For Indonesia, this means despite its growth and developmental strides, the leap to high-income status remains elusive.

Indonesia's journey through economic development has been marked by a series of obstacles that predated the leadership of President Joko Widodo (Jokowi). The nation's economic conditions prior to Jokowi's administration were characterized by moderate yet inconsistent growth. The GDP growth rate hovered around 5-6% annually during the early 2000s, which, while respectable, was insufficient to propel Indonesia into high-income status (Worldbank, n.d.). Despite this growth, structural inefficiencies plagued the economy. The public sector was burdened with bureaucratic red tape, hampering business operations and investment. According to the World Bank's Doing Business Report, Indonesia ranked 120th out of 183 countries in 2012, reflecting the challenges businesses faced in dealing with permits, regulations, and legal procedures (World Bank Group, n.d.). Infrastructure deficits were another critical issue. This lack of infrastructure hindered economic activities and stifled the overall growth potential. Not to mention, the economic model was heavily reliant on commodity exports, making Indonesia vulnerable to global market fluctuations. In 2013, for instance, the country faced a significant economic downturn when global commodity prices fell (Kementrian Energi dan Sumber Daya Mineral Republik Indonesia, 2013).

In the face of Indonesia's long standing economic hurdles, Jokowi's presidency brought a transformative approach aimed at driving the nation toward its vision of Indonesia Emas 2045 (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2023). This vision, which outlines Indonesia's aspirations to become a developed country by its centennial in 2045, underscores the importance of sustainable growth, innovation, and global competitiveness. Jokowi's administration recognized that to escape the "middle-income trap," Indonesia needed not only infrastructure development but also a comprehensive strategy that prioritized human capital. His policies were deeply intertwined with the goals of Indonesia Emas 2045, strengthening the nation's workforce (Saharani, 2023). By laying the groundwork for a future where the country could thrive both economically and socially, Jokowi aimed to position Indonesia as a formidable player on the global stage, with the foundations of Indonesia Emas 2045 as a guiding framework for progress (Sekretariat Kabinet Republik Indonesia, 2021).

Building on Jokowi's visionary approach to transforming Indonesia's economic landscape. This paper delves into the strategic efforts undertaken by his administration to escape the MIT, providing a detailed analysis of the policies and initiatives that have driven Indonesia's economic progression. By examining these strategies, this paper highlights the critical steps necessary for Indonesia and initiatives creates what is referred to as the snowball effect of economic development. Ultimately, this writing aims to elaborate and analyze the ongoing efforts in realizing Indonesia's economic potential to bridging the gap to high-income status. Thus, the author has prepared several research questions to help deepen the mindful discussion: (1) What measures has President Jokowi taken to rescue Indonesia from the clutches of the middle-income trap? (2) How have the gaps been successfully addressed through the implementation of President Jokowi's policies?

Literature Review

MIT has long been a heated debating topic. This was posed from numerous different views

among researchers. The Indonesian economy from 1976 to 2015 is highlighted by Hotmaria Elecktawati Lumbangaol in her paper "Existence and Determinants of Middle-Income Trap in Indonesia." The uneven distribution of income and status changes among Indonesians has resulted in slow growth, which raises the country's danger of being thrown into MIT. Poverty and inequality have also contributed to this stagnant state. The impact of the 1998 crisis on the Indonesian economy is covered in this article along with its numerous causes. (Lumbangaol, 2018, 84).

Even before Jokowi's administration, the previous Indonesian government had dealt with the same MIT matter. Since 2011, the Indonesian government has undertaken comprehensive and inclusive infrastructure development efforts known as MP3EI. Undoubtedly, this is extensively reviewed in Sigit Setiawan's publication entitled "Middle Income Trap and Infrastructure Issues in Indonesia: A Strategic Perspective". In order to escape MIT, the government has implemented a number of methods to accelerate infrastructure construction. Non-commercial public infrastructure construction increased considerably and faster than before in 2011, owing to the central government's involvement in infrastructure development through budget allocations and authority division with provinces. Jokowi's initiatives have indirectly raised budget allocations to increase responsibility for projects and the capacity of Indonesia's current human resources. (Setiawan, 2017)

A different perspective that might be looked into is whether education has a direct impact on Indonesia's productivity and GDP, as laid out by Tria Apriliana in her journal "Position Of Human Capital In Middle-Income Trap Countries (Case Study: Indonesia)". It is underlined that human capital serves a crucial role within the Indonesian economic development approach to depart from MIT. According to data from research in this publication, ages 16-18 are found to generate positive and productive GDP per capita. These findings reveal that the activity of Indonesia's young generation can fully contribute to the country's productivity numbers and, as a result, influence the value of GDP per capita. Whether or not Indonesia may be able to leave MIT is also determined by this aspect, particularly the productivity of human resources in producing a relatively high quality of living. This is a challenge in itself, as attending school can inhibit Indonesia's efforts to move out of MIT more rapidly. (Apriliana et al., 2021)

This is in line with the findings of Md. Jaber Al Islam's article titled "Escaping the middle-income trap: A study on a developing economy". This article examines Bangladesh's efforts to break out of the middle-class trap and achieve higher income levels. According to the research findings, Bangladesh will be able to exit MIT in 2029 and become a high-income country in 2041 if its GNI per capita grows by 9.69%. However, several risks emerge, such as disease outbreaks, natural disasters, political instability, and economic downturns, which impede the process of leaving MIT. Indirectly, this generates a different viewpoint for us as readers in the context of Indonesia, demonstrating that leaving MIT is not easy and will be brimming with significant hazards that could hamper the government's efforts. (Islam et al., 2023)

Limitless, Petrus Sepraldi Siregar also covered a different angle in his article "UMKM Kunci Indonesia Keluar Dari Middle Income Trap." Petrus emphasizes that Indonesia's efforts have not been successful in moving it out of the MIT zone since the government's focus on MSMEs management remains insufficient. Local culture and the potential of the region are still not being maximized. Petrus further emphasizes that MSMEs are a crucial factor in overcoming economic issues that exist amidst global problems and MSMEs are considered as the best solution. This paper provides effective suggestions for the Indonesian government to fully contribute by

making it easier for MSME owners to borrow capital in order to improve the quality and quantity of their products. With the hope, it can increase the rate of economic growth and Indonesia's GDP. (Siregar et al., 2021, 93).

2. Analytical Framework

Middle Income Trap

To steer the debate towards a more defined topic, an advanced framework of thought is required. The Middle-Income Trap (MIT) is a condition where countries that have successfully reached middle-income status experience difficulties in advancing to high-income status. Countries trapped in the MIT tend to face economic stagnation after reaching middle-income levels, thereby failing to achieve the necessary economic growth to become advanced economies. This concept was first introduced by Gill and Kharas in a World Bank report in 2007 (Gill & Kharas, 2007). According to their analysis, countries caught within the MIT exhibited rapid growth when it was in the low-income category. However, this growth is significantly slowing once they attain middle-income status.

Aiyar et al. in their paper "*Growth Slowdowns and the Middle-Income Trap*," published by the International Monetary Fund (IMF), elucidate those countries ensnared in MIT often demonstrate a marked deceleration in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth upon reaching middle-income status (Aiyar et al., 2013). Their findings indicate that reliance on low-value-added commodity exports, coupled with limited capacity for innovation and technology adoption, are primary factors leading these countries into the trap. Indicators that signify a country might be caught in the MIT encompass several dimensions.

Furthermore, Eichengreen, Park, and Shin, in their journal article "*Growth Slowdowns Redux: New Evidence on the Middle-Income Trap*," highlight those countries trapped in the MIT typically possess low innovation capacities and insufficient investment in education and workforce training (Eichengreen et al., 2013). The researchers emphasize that high innovation capacity and substantial investment in human capital are crucial for escaping MIT. Additionally, they stress the importance of economic diversification from commodity sectors to more advanced sectors. Income inequality also serves as a critical indicator of the MIT.

Felipe, Abdon, and Kumar, in their paper "*Tracking the Middle-Income Trap: What is it, Who is in it, and Why?*" was published by the Levy Economics Institute, has found that countries with significant income inequality are more susceptible to the MIT (Felipe, 2012). This inequality impedes inclusive and sustainable economic growth, as a substantial portion of the population does not benefit from economic advancements. Low-quality education and training systems are another significant factor. Countries caught in the MIT often have inadequate education and training systems, which hinder the ability of their workforce to adapt to technological changes and the increasingly complex demands of the labor market.

Thus, the MIT represents a multifaceted economic phenomenon where countries that have achieved middle-income status struggle to progress to high-income status. This stagnation in economic growth, after an initial period of rapid development, can be attributed to several key factors. These include a slowdown in GDP growth, over-reliance on low-value-added commodity exports, limited capacity for innovation and technology adoption, significant income inequality, and inadequate education and training systems. Understanding these indicators and their impact on economic progression is crucial for analyzing the challenges faced by countries caught in the MIT like Indonesia.

Liberal

Interventionism

The involvement of President Jokowi during his two terms also could be seen from the lens of International Relations (IR), as being extremely important, hence this theory is appropriate to characterize the topic of this research. In "Global Political Economy," Theodore H. Cohn highlights the specifics of liberal interventionism. Liberal interventionists contend that since markets sometimes fail to produce the most profits and most widespread benefits, negative freedom is insufficient (Cohn & Hira, 2020, 78). Therefore, in a free market economy, government involvement is urgently necessary for fostering justice and equality. This unexpected notion came from British economist John Maynard Keynes, who believed that government intervention is used to save, revive and maximize capitalism, not to replace it. The idea of liberal interventionism further highlights the importance of social democracy, equality, and freedom. It also emphasizes that the international economic system can only operate effectively if it is based on market mechanisms and prices (Cohn & Hira, 2020, 79). Given the study in this work, this theory is ideally suited to characterize and guide the path of the debate.

Jokowi's intervention or more precisely "contribution" over the 10 years from 2014-2024 has been seen as a green light that Indonesia is trying hard to leave MIT by implementing industrial policy. Industrial policy is defined as government intervention in the business world to strengthen a country's economic activities in the short term to produce long-term impacts (OECD, n.d.). The government uses industrial policy, especially for companies, to overcome existing economic challenges, which cannot be overcome by the market alone. Therefore, the Jokowi government's intervention is crucially needed.

Figure 1. Framework for Escaping the Middle-Income Trap: A Policy Intervention Approach (2014-2024).
Source: Created by author.

3. Research Method

This chapter outlines the methodological framework used to conduct the research and ensure that the study achieves its intended objectives. The chosen research methodology plays a critical role in shaping the direction of the study, influencing both the data collection and the analytical processes. Methodology refers to the systematic approaches and techniques employed to explore and understand the research topic in depth (Sreekumar, 2023). To provide a structured and thorough examination of the subject, this chapter is divided into four sections: Research Type, Types and Sources of Data, Data Collection Techniques, and Data Analysis Techniques.

Research Type

The research adopts a qualitative approach as the most appropriate method for examining the chosen topic. Qualitative research is known for its ability to explore complex issues by delving into assumptions, worldviews, and theoretical perspectives (Creswell, 2007, p. 37). This approach is particularly relevant for analyzing Indonesia's efforts, especially President Joko Widodo's initiatives to escape the MIT. Through qualitative research, the study seeks to uncover deeper insights into the challenges and strategies involved in this process. The case study method is employed to focus on two periods of Jokowi's administration, enabling the researcher to evaluate his ten-year tenure, summarize his achievements, and assess whether his efforts have successfully guided Indonesia out of the MIT.

Types and Sources of Data

This research relies primarily on secondary data as the main source of information. Secondary data includes documents, reports, interviews, and other pre-existing resources that are analyzed to provide insights into the research questions. The data are gathered from credible sources such as government websites, academic journals, online libraries like JSTOR, and other reputable platforms. By utilizing secondary data, the research ensures that a comprehensive and well-rounded analysis is conducted without the need for direct fieldwork.

Data Collection Techniques

Data collection is carried out through a detailed review of **secondary sources**, including academic publications, government reports, and policy documents. These sources are selected based on their relevance to the research topic and their potential to provide a rich understanding of Indonesia's economic development under President Jokowi. Online databases and libraries, such as JSTOR, Google Scholar, and official government websites, serve as the primary tools for gathering the necessary data. This method allows for the collection of extensive information from a wide range of reliable sources.

Data Analysis Techniques

The data analysis process in this research follows a case study technique. The qualitative data collected from secondary sources are analyzed to identify patterns, relationships, and underlying themes related to Indonesia's efforts to overcome the MIT. The case study method, focusing on Jokowi's two administrative terms, allows for an in-depth examination of his policies and their effectiveness. The analysis also includes the comparison of Indonesia's performance against established economic indicators and benchmarks to determine whether the country has made significant progress in escaping the MIT.

4. Discussion

Industrial policy stands as one of the most potent strategies for accelerating economic development and tackling the myriad structural challenges that developing nations face. In the context of Indonesia's efforts to break free from the MIT, Jokowi's administration's initiatives provide a compelling example when examined through the prism of Liberal Interventionism. The administration has strategically embraced this approach, making it a fundamental pillar in Indonesia's bid to overcome MIT. Through a series of policies aimed at boosting industrial sector competitiveness, fostering investment, promoting innovation, and refining regulation, Jokowi seeks to establish a robust foundation for sustained economic growth.

Stated in chapter 2, Liberal Interventionism involves a spectrum of government interventions designed to reshape the economic structure and enhance the competitiveness of the industrial sector. Jokowi's approach is characterized by a structured and sustainable methodology, where each policy is meticulously crafted to systematically address various indicators of the MIT. This analysis will be divided into two distinct periods: the first term (2014-2019) and the second term (2020-2024). Each section will elucidate how the policies implemented during these periods were designed to address the indicators of the MIT, as elaborated in Chapter 2. In particular, the discussion will be developed in order to properly address the research question above.

2014-2019: A New Era of Connectivity

At the beginning of his tenure in 2014-2015, Jokowi focused significantly on infrastructure development. Massive infrastructure projects across various sectors became a top priority as an initial step to strengthen Indonesia's economic foundation. Key policies implemented during this period included the construction of toll roads and transportation networks. The government accelerated the development of toll roads, ports, airports, and railway networks to enhance regional connectivity. Data from the Ministry of Public Works and Public Housing (PUPR) indicate that by the end of 2015, approximately 200 kilometers of new toll roads had been constructed (Kementrian Pekerjaan Umum dan Perumahan Rakyat, 2015). These projects included the construction of the Trans-Java toll road connecting Jakarta to Surabaya and the development of major ports such as Kuala Tanjung Port in North Sumatra and Makassar New Port in South Sulawesi (Pelindo, 2024). By improving connectivity, the government aimed to bridge regional disparities and facilitate more efficient movement of goods and people. One of the indicators of the MIT is **slowing GDP growth**. By enhancing infrastructure, the government sought to spur economic growth through increased investment and logistical efficiency. According to OECD data, adequate infrastructure can lower distribution costs and improve the competitiveness of domestic products (OECD, 2007).

In 2015, Jokowi launched an ambitious project to increase national electricity capacity by 35,000 MW (Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources, 2015). This project involved building new power plants and expanding the electricity distribution network across Indonesia. The goal was to meet the growing energy demands driven by industrial growth and urbanization. According to data from PLN (the state electricity company), by the end of 2015, approximately 7,000 MW of new power plant capacity had entered the construction phase (Pt. PLN, 2016). **Limited innovation capacity** is another indicator of MIT. Improved electricity availability is expected to foster industrial and technological innovation, thereby boosting national productivity and competitiveness. Reducing economic inequality also became a major priority during this period. The government launched various social protection programs such as the Kartu Indonesia Pintar (KIP) and the Kartu Indonesia Sehat (KIS) to provide more equitable

access to education and health services (Kominfo, 2014). These programs aimed to reduce **income disparities** and ensure that all societal layers could benefit from economic growth. By reducing income inequality, the government sought to create more inclusive and sustainable economic growth. These steps indicate that in the 2014-2015 period, Jokowi focused on strengthening infrastructure as a foundation for promoting sustainable economic growth and overcoming obstacles that hinder Indonesia from escaping the MIT.

After laying the groundwork for infrastructure during his early tenure, Jokowi's administration shifted its focus in the 2016-2017 period towards accelerating the implementation of national strategic projects. This period marked a stronger commitment to completing major projects aimed at enhancing Indonesia's competitiveness and economic growth. Jokowi accelerated the implementation of National Strategic Projects (PSN) to expedite development and reduce economic disparities between regions (Humas, 2016). PSN encompassed various large-scale infrastructure projects deemed vital for long-term economic growth and equitable development. According to data from the Coordinating Ministry for Economic Affairs, there were 225 projects and one program included within PSN in 2016, with a total investment value of IDR 4,197 trillion (Pencapaian Proyek Strategis Nasional, 2019). This effort was also supported by enhanced coordination between central and regional governments, as well as the establishment of the Committee for the Acceleration of Priority Infrastructure Provision (KPPIP) to ensure the smooth implementation of strategic projects. This initiative was expected to sustain and enhance economic growth, with **slowing GDP growth** being a primary indicator of the MIT.

During this period, the government also introduced alternative financing schemes such as Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) to attract private investment in infrastructure projects (Noor, 2016). Through PPP, the government aimed to reduce reliance on state budgets by involving the private sector in financing, constructing, and operating infrastructure projects. By the end of 2017, 30 PPP projects had reached financial close, with a total investment value of approximately IDR 234 trillion, including major projects such as the Trans-Sumatra Toll Road and the Jakarta-Bandung high-speed railway project (Rodrigo, 2023). PPP was designed to promote investment in manufacturing and services sectors, which was expected to reduce Indonesia's reliance on low value-added commodity exports. This was an important step in addressing one of the MIT indicators, namely **dependence on low-value commodity exports**. Overall, the measures taken by Jokowi's administration in the 2016-2017 period demonstrated a strong commitment to accelerating strategic infrastructure development as part of efforts to escape MIT. Through these policies, the government aimed to create a more conducive environment for investment, improve logistical efficiency, and promote sustainable economic growth.

Continuing the acceleration of national strategic projects from the previous period, Jokowi's administration in the 2018-2019 period shifted its focus to regulatory and bureaucratic reforms to create a better business climate. These reforms aimed to improve government efficiency, attract investment, and address various constraints hindering economic growth. One of the main policies during this period was the simplification of business licensing. Through the implementation of the Online Single Submission (OSS) system, the government streamlined the business licensing process by integrating various permits into a single online platform (Kominfo, 2018). The OSS was designed to reduce the time and cost required to obtain business permits, thereby enhancing ease of doing business in Indonesia. This system was expected to encourage

more innovation and investment from the private sector, addressing the issue of **limited innovation capacity**, a key indicator of the MIT.

Additionally, the government increased its focus on education and vocational training reforms (Kominfo, 2019). These programs were designed to ensure that Indonesian workers had skills relevant to industry needs. By improving the quality and accessibility of vocational education, the government hoped to create a more competitive and productive workforce. This effort was a crucial step in addressing the **inadequacy of education and training systems**, another indicator of the MIT. Furthermore, World Bank data indicates that regulatory and bureaucratic reforms during this period successfully improved Indonesia's ease of doing business ranking from 91st in 2016 to 73rd in 2019 (World Bank Group, n.d.). This improvement shows that the government's efforts to simplify regulations and enhance bureaucratic efficiency began to yield positive results. The measures taken by Jokowi's administration in the 2018-2019 period demonstrate a strong commitment to creating a better business climate through regulatory and bureaucratic reforms. By simplifying licensing, enhancing vocational education, and reducing economic inequality, the government aimed to address various indicators of the MIT and promote more inclusive and sustainable economic growth..

2019-2024: Towards a Resilient Nation

In his second term, Jokowi announced his goals for developing human resources and the digital economy. At the beginning of 2019-2020, Jokowi prioritized human resource development as a means of developing the digital economy, building competent human resources, mastering science and technology, and inviting global talent to collaborate with the government. Jokowi believes that strengthening human resources can encourage economic growth and the country must not lose its demographic bonus. The focus on human resources is expected to produce innovative ideas and opportunities amidst rapid global development. By developing human resources and mastering technology optimally, the problem of weak management of natural resources can be overcome by the government (Rony, 2019). The APBN allocation of 20% of the government budget is a concrete manifestation of the government's efforts to improve the quality of Indonesia's human resources. This budget is intended, among other things, for Smart Indonesia, School Operational Assistance, school infrastructure development, and the provision of BidikMisi Scholarships (Nugroho, 2020). By focusing on developing human resources, especially education and infrastructure, this is an effort to overcome one of MIT's many indicators, namely **limited innovation capacity** and **inadequate education and training systems**.

During Jokowi's second term, especially in 2020-2021, an unexpected pandemic occurred which disrupted all activities from schools to the business world. The COVID-19 outbreak had practically changed the entire direction of policy, causing Indonesia to face an economic disaster (Melati, 2023). During the epidemic, Jokowi shifted his policies to focus more on economic recovery and social reform, as outlined in the 2021 Government Work Plan. The dealing process with the COVID-19 epidemic was split into three stages: Economic Rescue (2020), Supporting Economic Recovery (2021), and Economic Recovery and Structural Reform (2022). The government provided financial support to the community through tax relief, installment postponement rules, and interest subsidies for the business actor (Kementerian Perencanaan Pembangunan Nasional, 2021). The government established the COVID-19 Handling and National Economic Recovery Committee (KPC-PEN), which was initially focused on dealing

with COVID-19 Acceleration Handling Task Force (Kementerian Koordinator Bidang Perekonomian Republik Indonesia, n.d.) under COVID-19

As of May 11th, 2021, KPC-PEN had created the National Economic Recovery Program (PEN) which cost IDR 172.35 trillion. (Sekretariat Kabinet Republik Indonesia, 2021). Airlangga, Chairman of KPC-PEN, had stated that this realization includes the Health Program of IDR 24.9 trillion, or 14.2% of the highest limit. Priority programs totaled IDR 21.8 trillion, or 17.6% of the limit. This policy addresses the MIT indicator, namely **slowing GDP growth** being a major indicator of the MIT, which was impacted during the COVID-19 period. The government had raised the health budget to address COVID-19, which includes vaccination distribution and hospital renovations. This initiative targeted **inadequacy of education and training systems**, which is one of the MIT indicators, growing health sector capacity also entails training medical people and strengthening health facilities. Meanwhile, the MSME and Corporate Support Program achieved IDR 42.03 trillion and the Business Incentive Program achieved IDR 26.83 trillion. The Social Protection Program (Perlinsos) cost IDR 56.79 trillion with details on the Family Hope Program (PKH), the Basic Food Card, Cash Social Assistance, and Village BLT. COVID-19 has led many individuals to lose their jobs; these enterprises are able to provide financial help to communities, particularly those affected by COVID-19, including in MIT instruments where **income disparity** is an issue. The government's efforts to control the COVID-19 pandemic appear to have had adequate benefits, as seen by Indonesia's national economic growth, which rose to 3.69% in 2021. With this growth rate, Indonesia's GDP per capita grew to IDR 62.2 million (or comparable to US\$ 4,349.5), surpassing the GDP per capita prior to the pandemic, which was IDR 59.3 million in 2019. Indonesia's national economic growth rose in 2022, reaching 5.31%, the highest level since 2013, when it was 5.56%. The increase in Indonesia's national economic growth is supported by trade considerations, specifically exports, which increased by 16.28% and imports by 14.75% (Kementerian Koordinator Bidang Perekonomian, 2022).

In 2023-2024, the government is increasing investment since it has a significant impact on the national economy. Regulations are required to ensure the existing and hospitable investment process to exit MIT. A country's economic development is heavily reliant on investment, particularly in terms of maintaining steady and sustainable state growth that enhances people's welfare (Sugiarto, 2024). The Indonesian government's policy strategies include improving regulations and facilitating procedures through the Job Creation Law (UUCK), which simplifies business licensing, as well as various forms of tax incentives such as tax breaks, tax holidays, investment allowances for labor incentives, and super deductions for vocational and research programs. To stimulate investment enthusiasm in supporting sustainable economic growth of Indonesia, it is vital to continue to push the optimization of UUCK implementation as a vehicle for economic transformation toward Indonesia. Indonesia has also created a strategic industrial ecosystem by implementing a downstreaming policy for commodities like bauxite, tin, nickel, and others, ensuring that they have high added value and durability. This is related to Indonesia's goal of becoming one of the world's largest producers of electric vehicles while also developing a robust ecosystem (Pemerintah Akselerasi Peningkatan Investasi Dalam Upaya Keluar Dari Jebakan Negara Berpenghasilan Menengah, 2023). The policy taken by Jokowi to reduce this dependency is by adding value through processing raw materials before exporting. This is an important step in overcoming one of the indicators of the MIT, namely **dependence on low-**

value commodity

exports. Jokowi's

efforts so far have not been able to get Indonesia out of MIT. Indonesia still needs to work hard to improve its infrastructure economy if it wants to leave MIT completely. With the current growth rate of 5%, economic transformation still requires improvement. In a transformative scenario, Indonesia's exit from MIT in 2041 requires an average growth rate of 6%. Even in the best scenario, Indonesia will not be able to escape from MIT until 2038 unless Indonesia reaches an average growth rate of 7% (Sugiarto, 2024).

Policy Impact on Indonesia's Stagnancy

INDICATORS	PERIODS					
	2014-2019			2019-2024		
	2014-2015	2016-2017	2018-2019	2019-2020	2021-2022	2023-2024
Slowing GDP Growth	Enhancing Infrastructure	Accelerated the Implementation of National Strategic Projects (PSN)			National Economic Recovery Program (PEN)	
Dependence on Low Value-Added Commodity exports		Public-Private Partnerships (PPP)				Job Creation Law (UUCK)
Limited Innovation Capacity	Increase National Electricity		Online Single Submission (OSS) system	Educational Programs		
Significant Income Disparities	Social Protection Programs				MISME and Corporate Support Program	
Inadequate Education and Training Systems			Education and Vocational Training Reforms	Educational Programs	Training Medical People and Strengthening Health Facilities	

Table 1. Overcoming the Middle-Income Trap: Economic Development Initiatives under Joko Widodo's Administration.

Source: Created by author.

Indonesia's journey toward escaping the MIT under Jokowi's administration can be critically assessed by examining the development of five key indicators that have historically constrained the nation's economic growth. The evaluation of these indicators provides insight into the extent to which the government has effectively addressed these obstacles. Prior to delving into the detailed assessment, it is essential to consider the table that encapsulates the timeline and categorization of the government's strategic initiatives.

The table serves as an analytical framework, outlining the distinct periods between 2014-2019 and 2019-2024. It provides a systematic approach, categorizing policy interventions aimed at mitigating key challenges. Each indicator represents a critical component of the MIT, and the government's policy, displayed in the table, highlights targeted reforms and programs to overcome barriers and foster sustainable economic growth.

a) Slowing GDP Growth

During Jokowi's tenure, Indonesia's GDP growth has shown both resilience and vulnerability, reflecting the complex dynamics of an emerging economy striving to break free from the Middle-Income Trap. From 2014 to 2019, Indonesia's GDP growth consistently averaged around 5% annually. While this was a modest improvement compared to the global average for emerging markets, it remained below the ambitious 7% target often cited by economists as necessary for substantial poverty alleviation and

broader economic transformation. This growth rate, while stable, indicated the challenges Indonesia faced in scaling up its economic output to a level that would propel it into high-income status.

The economic stability seen during the early years of Jokowi's administration was abruptly disrupted by the COVID-19 pandemic. The global health crisis severely impacted all sectors of Indonesia's economy, leading to a contraction of -2.1% in 2020 (World Bank, 2020). The pandemic exposed structural vulnerabilities, such as the heavy reliance on consumer spending and the limited diversification of the economy. However, Jokowi's government responded with stimulus packages aimed at protecting the most vulnerable segments of the population, as well as supporting businesses, which played a crucial role in stabilizing the economy.

In 2021, the Indonesian economy began its recovery, with GDP growth rebounding to approximately 3.7%, and further accelerating to 5.3% in 2023 (World Bank Group, 2023). This recovery, though significant, was still modest when compared to pre-pandemic targets and was primarily driven by a resurgence in domestic consumption, government spending, and a recovery in exports. However, the pace of this growth has been moderate, highlighting that while Indonesia has made strides in overcoming the immediate impacts of the pandemic, the underlying structural challenges remain. The current growth trajectory suggests that Indonesia is on the path to recovery, but the rate of progress is insufficient to decisively break free from the Middle-Income Trap.

b) Dependence on Low-Value-Added Commodity Exports

Indonesia's economic structure has long been characterized by its dependence on the export of low-value-added commodities, such as coal, palm oil, and unprocessed minerals. These commodities have traditionally driven export revenues but have also made the economy vulnerable to global price fluctuations and limited its capacity for industrial transformation. Under President Jokowi's leadership, efforts to reduce this reliance have yielded some progress, though the pace of change has been gradual.

From 2014 to 2024, the output of manufacturing in Indonesia's GDP grew modestly from \$187.74B to around \$241.87B (Macrotrends, 2024). This shift, though incremental, reflects a slow but ongoing transition towards higher-value-added production. A significant driver of this change has been the government's push for downstream processing of raw materials. The ban on raw nickel exports, implemented to encourage domestic processing industries, is a notable example of this strategy. As a result, Indonesia has seen a surge in the export of processed nickel products, which has contributed to the diversification of its export base and the growth of industries like battery manufacturing for electric vehicles.

However, despite these advancements, Indonesia's export profile continues to be dominated by commodities such as coal and palm oil. In 2022, these two commodities alone accounted for over 20% of the country's total exports (OEC World, 2023). This heavy reliance on low-value-added exports underscores the ongoing challenges Indonesia faces in achieving a more balanced and resilient economy. The continued dominance of such commodities in the export structure suggests that, while there has been some diversification, it has not been sufficient to significantly reduce the economy's vulnerability to external shocks or to fully propel Indonesia towards higher-value-added

industrialization.

The slow pace of structural transformation in Indonesia's export economy indicates that while progress is being made, it remains insufficient to escape the MIT fully.

c) Limited Innovation Capacity

Indonesia's innovation capacity has seen some advancements during President Jokowi's administration, yet it continues to lag behind global standards, especially when compared to other rapidly developing economies. The country's ranking in the Global Innovation Index (GII) slightly improved from 87th in 2014 to 75th in 2022 (ANTARA, 2023), reflecting modest progress in areas such as infrastructure, market sophistication, and knowledge and technology outputs. However, this incremental improvement highlights the significant challenges Indonesia still faces in fostering a robust innovation ecosystem.

One of the primary indicators of a country's innovation capacity is its investment in research and development (R&D). In Indonesia, R&D expenditure has consistently remained low, at approximately 0.3% of GDP, far below the levels seen in innovation leaders like China and South Korea, where R&D spending exceeds 2% and 4% of GDP, respectively (Akhlas, 2020). This disparity in investment is a major constraint on Indonesia's ability to generate new technologies, patents, and high-value products. The limited financial commitment to R&D not only hampers the development of advanced industries but also restricts the country's capacity to improve productivity and competitiveness on a global scale.

Despite these challenges, there are positive trends within specific sectors that signal potential for future growth in innovation. The rise of the digital economy, particularly the rapid expansion of tech startups and e-commerce platforms, illustrates a burgeoning innovation environment. Companies like Gojek and Tokopedia have become prominent players in the Southeast Asian tech scene (investinasia, 2023), demonstrating that Indonesia has the potential to nurture homegrown innovation, particularly in the digital space. This growth has been fueled by a young, tech-savvy population and increasing internet penetration (Tran, 2024), which have both created a fertile ground for digital innovation. While there have been improvements in Indonesia's innovation capacity during Jokowi's presidency, significant gaps remain.

d) Significant Income Disparities

Under President Jokowi's administration, Indonesia has made some strides in addressing income inequality, though the challenge remains substantial. One of the key indicators of income inequality is the Gini coefficient, which measures the distribution of income across a population. A lower Gini coefficient suggests a more equitable distribution of income. During Jokowi's presidency, Indonesia's Gini coefficient improved from 0.414 in 2014 to 0.384 in 2022 (Office of Assistant to Deputy Cabinet Secretary for State, 2019). This decline reflects a reduction in income inequality, indicating that, on a broad level, efforts to create a more inclusive economy have had some success. Accompanying this improvement in income distribution has been a notable reduction in poverty rates. In 2014, 11.3% of Indonesia's population lived below the poverty line (Indonesia Investment, 2014). By 2023, this figure had decreased to 9.36% (BPS - Statistics Indonesia, 2023). This achievement is significant, as it highlights the resilience of Indonesia's social safety nets and economic policies in protecting the

most vulnerable segments of society, even during periods of global crisis.

However, these aggregate improvements mask persistent and deep-rooted disparities that continue to challenge the country's development trajectory. Significant income gaps remain between urban and rural populations, as well as between different regions of the country. Urban areas, particularly on the island of Java, continue to see faster economic growth and greater access to infrastructure, education, and healthcare compared to rural and less developed regions like Papua. This uneven distribution of wealth and opportunities exacerbates regional inequalities and highlights the limitations of current policies in achieving equitable development across the archipelago. The progress in reducing income disparities, while commendable, has been gradual, and the pace of change suggests that inequality remains a substantial barrier to overcoming the MIT.

e) **Inadequate Education and Training Systems**

Indonesia's education and training systems have seen notable improvements during President Jokowi's tenure, yet they continue to face significant challenges that hinder the country's progress towards becoming a high-income economy. On the positive side, access to education has increased, as evidenced by the rise in the enrollment rate in secondary education from 78% in 2014 to 84% in 2022 (OECD, 2023). This growth in enrollment reflects the government's efforts to make education more accessible to a larger segment of the population, particularly in rural and underserved areas. Additionally, Indonesia's Human Development Index (HDI) rose from 0.687 in 2014 to 0.713 in 2023 (Zain, 2024), highlighting overall improvements in key areas such as education, life expectancy, and income per capita.

However, despite these gains in enrollment and human development, the quality of education in Indonesia remains a significant concern. The country's performance in international assessments, such as the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), reveals the gaps in the effectiveness of the education system. In the 2022 PISA rankings, Indonesia was placed 69th out of 81 countries (PISA, 2022), indicating that students in Indonesia are lagging their peers in critical areas such as reading, mathematics, and science. This performance suggests that while more students are attending school, the education they are receiving is not adequately preparing them for the demands of a modern workforce. While Indonesia has made strides in expanding access to education and improving overall human development, the quality and relevance of its education and training systems remain inadequate to fully support the country's aspirations of becoming a high-income economy.

Overall, these advances indicate that Indonesia is moving in the right direction, the remaining gaps highlight the need for continued and focused efforts. Jokowi's policies have laid a solid foundation, but sustained and intensified reforms will be crucial for Indonesia to overcome the MIT and achieve long-term economic prosperity, towards Indonesia Emas 2045.

In Indonesia Emas 2045 vision, several numerical targets have been set to be achieved by Indonesia by that year. These targets are selected by author focus on economic growth. The following are some of the key targets:

1. Per Capita Income: Indonesia aims to achieve a per capita income of USD

23,000 - USD

30,000. This would signify the nation's exit from the middle-income trap and its transition into a high-income, developed country (Kristianus, 2023).

2. **Nominal GDP:** Indonesia's economy is projected to reach a total of USD 9.8 trillion, placing the country among the top five global economies (Kementerian Koordinator Bidang Perekonomian, 2023).
3. **Poverty Rate:** The goal is to reduce the poverty rate to nearly zero percent, ensuring that all citizens can enjoy a decent standard of living (RONS, 2023).
4. **Unemployment Rate:** The target is to reduce the unemployment rate to below 4%, reflecting stability in the labor market and increased workforce productivity (Herwantoko, 2024).

Indonesia's vision for Indonesia Emas 2045 presents ambitious targets to transform the country into a high-income, globally competitive economy by the centennial of its independence. To reach these objectives, significant progress is needed across key economic indicators. Analyzing Indonesia's current position and projecting future growth requires examining the necessary conditions and actions that could enable the country to meet these targets, nevertheless, to understand Indonesia's progress under Jokowi administration in the context of the Indonesia Emas 2045 targets. The following elaborates on each indicator, outlining realistic scenarios and the essential growth trajectories required.

1) Per Capita Income

- Before Jokowi (2013): Per capita income in Indonesia approximately USD 3,667.
- During Jokowi (2023): By 2023, this figure increased to around USD 4,942 (O'Neill, 2024).

This represents a growth of about 35% over a decade, indicating gradual improvement. However, to achieve the Indonesia Emas 2045 target of USD 23,000 to USD 30,000, Indonesia must significantly accelerate its per capita income growth, aiming for nearly a fivefold to sixfold increase over the next two decades.

Growth Scenario

To calculate the required growth rate, it needed to assess how much per capita income must grow annually to reach the lower bound of the Indonesia Emas 2045 target, USD 23,000, by 2045. Using the exponential growth formula:

$$FV = PV \times (1 + r)^t$$

Where,

- FV is the future value or the target per capita income (USD 23,000).
- PV is the present value or the current per capita income (USD 4,942 in 2023).
- r is the annual growth rate to be determined.
- t is the number of years between 2023 and 2045 (22 years).

$$23000 = 4942 \times (1 + r)^{22}$$

$$\frac{23000}{4942} = (1 + r)^{22}$$

$$4.65 = (1 + r)^{22}$$

$$4.65^{\frac{1}{22}} = 1 + r$$

$$1.0723 = 1 + r$$

$$r = 0.0723 = 7.23\%$$

Figure 2. Calculation for Growth to Reach the Per Capita Income Target.
Calculation: Processed by author.

Thus,

- Annual per capita income growth must reach at least 7.23% to meet the 2045 lowest target, which is substantially higher than the average growth rate of around 3.02% per year seen during Jokowi's administration. The current pace is not sufficient, highlighting the need for a more aggressive economic strategy.
- The key to accelerating this growth lies in enhancing productivity across sectors, particularly through investments in technology, human capital, and innovation.
- Before Jokowi, Indonesia relied heavily on low-cost manufacturing and primary commodities, whereas during Jokowi's administration, efforts have been made to diversify the economy, but more needs to be done to drive income growth in the long term (Warburton et al., 2021).

2) Nominal GDP

- Before Jokowi (2013): Indonesia's nominal GDP was approximately USD 912.5 billion.
- During Jokowi (2023): By 2023, nominal GDP had grown to around USD 1.37 trillion (Trading Economics, 2024).

This represents a growth of approximately 50.2% over the course of ten years. While this growth is notable, it remains below the pace required to meet the Indonesia Emas 2045 target of achieving USD 9.8 trillion in nominal GDP. To reach this target, Indonesia's GDP must grow by nearly sevenfold over the next two decades.

Growth Scenario

To determine the required growth rate to reach USD 9.8 trillion by 2045, the exponential growth formula is applied:

$$FV = PV \times (1 + r)^t$$

Where,

- FV is the future value or the target nominal GDP (USD 9.8 trillion).
- PV is the present value or the current nominal GDP (USD 1.37 trillion in 2023).
- r is the annual growth rate to be calculated.
- t is the number of years between 2023 and 2045 (22 years).

$$9.8 = 1.37 \times (1 + r)^{22}$$

$$\frac{9.8}{1.37} = (1 + r)^{22}$$

$$7.153 = (1 + r)^{22}$$

$$7.153^{\frac{1}{22}} = 1 + r$$

$$1.0935 = 1 + r$$

$$r = 0.0935 = 9.35\%$$

Figure 3. Calculation for Growth to Reach the Nominal GDP Target.
Calculation: Processed by author.

Thus,

- The current growth rate of nominal GDP from 2013 to 2023 is approximately 4.3% annually, which is significantly below the required rate to reach the Indonesia Emas 2045 target. To achieve a nominal GDP of USD 9.8 trillion by 2045, Indonesia's economy needs to grow at an average annual rate of approximately 9.35% over the next 22 years. Several key factors must be addressed to accelerate growth.
- Future growth will require a deeper shift towards industrial diversification, particularly in advanced manufacturing, digital services, and green technologies. These sectors can help Indonesia move up the global value chain and expand its economic base.
- Before Jokowi, Indonesia's growth was driven largely by commodities and labor-intensive manufacturing, whereas during Jokowi's administration, the focus has shifted to infrastructure development, investment in digital industries, and increased foreign investment (Office of Assistant to Deputy Cabinet Secretary for State Documents & Translation, 2017).

3) Poverty Rate

- Before Jokowi (2013): Indonesia's poverty rate stood at approximately 11.3% (Febriady et al., 2013).
- During Jokowi (2023): By 2023, the poverty rate had declined to around 9.36% (Indonesia, 2023).

This represents a reduction of 1.94 percentage points over ten years, a modest improvement. While this reduction is positive, the poverty rate is still far from the ambitious Indonesia Emas 2045 target of reducing the poverty rate to nearly 0%. To reach this target, the pace of poverty reduction must accelerate.

Growth Scenario

To demonstrate the calculation of how poverty could be reduced further, an example of aiming for a 1% poverty rate by 2045 is considered. Using the exponential decay formula for the reduction of the poverty rate:

$$FV = PV \times e^{-r \times t}$$

Where,

- PV is the present value of the poverty rate (9.36% in 2023),
- FV is the future value of the poverty rate (1% by 2045),
- r is the annual reduction rate (to be calculated),
- t is the number of years between 2023 and 2045 (22 years).

$$1 = 9.36 \times e^{-r \times 22}$$

$$\frac{1}{9.36} = e^{-r \times 22}$$

$$0.106837 = e^{-r \times 22}$$

$$\ln(0.106837) = -r \times 22$$

$$-2.2310 = -r \times 22$$

$$r = \frac{2.2310}{22}$$

$$r = 0.1016 = 10.16\%$$

Figure 4. Calculation for Decay to Reach the Poverty Rate Target.
Calculation: Processed by author.

Thus,

- To reduce the poverty rate from 9.36% in 2023 to 1% by 2045, Indonesia would need to achieve an average annual poverty reduction rate of 10.16%. This is significantly faster than the current rate of decline, which has been around 0.19 percentage points annually over the past decade.
- To eliminate poverty, Indonesia must focus on inclusive economic growth that targets the most vulnerable populations. The current poverty reduction rate needs to accelerate, with an emphasis on job creation, education, and rural development.
- Before Jokowi, poverty reduction was driven by basic subsidies and increased agricultural productivity (Engagement, 2016). During Jokowi, additional measures such as social assistance programs (e.g., the Family Hope Program) and infrastructure projects aimed at creating jobs and improving access to markets have contributed to poverty alleviation (Suryahadi & Izzati, 2018).
- However, moving forward, addressing income inequality and enhancing social protection programs will be critical in driving the poverty rate closer to zero.

4) Poverty Rate

- Before Jokowi (2013): Indonesia's unemployment rate stood at approximately 6.17%.
- During Jokowi (2023): By 2023, the unemployment rate had declined to around 5.32% (Trading Economics, 2024).

This reduction of 0.85 percentage points over ten years shows gradual improvement. The Indonesia Emas 2045 target aims to reduce the unemployment rate to below 4%, a more

accelerated
and labor market reforms will be necessary.

pace of job creation

Growth Scenario

For the purpose of calculation, a more ambitious target of 3% will be used to demonstrate the level of effort required. To estimate how the unemployment rate can be reduced to 3% by 2045, the exponential decay formula is used:

$$FV = PV \times e^{-r \times t}$$

Where,

- PV is the present value of the unemployment rate (5.32% in 2023),
- FV is the future value of the unemployment rate (3% by 2045),
- r is the annual reduction rate (to be calculated),
- t is the number of years between 2023 and 2045 (22 years).

$$3 = 5.32 \times e^{-r \times 22}$$

$$\frac{3}{5.32} = e^{-r \times 22}$$

$$0.56391 = e^{-r \times 22}$$

$$\ln(0.56391) = -r \times 22$$

$$-0.5733 = -r \times 22$$

$$r = \frac{0.5733}{22}$$

$$r = 0.02604 = 2.60\%$$

Figure 5. Calculation for Decay to Reach the Unemployment Rate Target.
Calculation: Processed by author.

Thus,

- To reduce the unemployment rate from 5.32% in 2023 to below 4% by 2045, with a calculation example using 3%, Indonesia must achieve an average annual reduction rate of approximately **2.6%**.
- To eliminate unemployment to below 4%, Indonesia must generate millions of new jobs annually, particularly in sectors like technology, tourism, services, and manufacturing. A stronger focus on labor market reforms is needed to address underemployment and improve job quality.
- Before Jokowi, unemployment was driven by structural issues in the labor market, such as mismatches between education and job market needs (Allen et al., 2018). During Jokowi's administration, policies have aimed at improving vocational training and supporting entrepreneurship, though more needs to be done to bridge the skills gap and ensure that job creation keeps pace with economic growth (Office of Assistant to Deputy Cabinet Secretary for State Documents & Translation, 2020).
- A key challenge moving forward will be addressing youth unemployment and ensuring that new graduates are equipped with the skills needed for the digital economy.

5. Conclusion

"Untuk jadi maju memang banyak tantangan dan hambatan. Kecewa semenit dua menit boleh. Tetapi setelah itu harus bangkit lagi," said the President of Indonesia, Joko Widodo.

Jokowi's administration has demonstrated a significant commitment to make Indonesia greater, overcoming the MIT, a challenge that often prevents developing countries from achieving advanced economic status. Through the lens of industrial policy theory, this effort underscores the crucial role of the state in fostering inclusive and sustainable economic development. During Jokowi's first term (2014-2019), the primary focus was on infrastructure development. In the second term (2019-2024), the focus shifted to human resource development and the digital economy.

These policies have successfully addressed some gaps. Jokowi's strategy illustrates a "snowball effect" in economic development, where each stage of development produces sustainable impacts that reinforce the foundation for subsequent steps. Massive infrastructure development at the beginning of his administration created better connectivity and supported economic efficiency. Regulatory and bureaucratic reforms then strengthened the business environment, enhancing investment attractiveness. In the second term, human resource development ensured the availability of a competitive workforce in the digital economy era. The effective response to the pandemic demonstrated economic resilience, while the promotion of investment and economic diversification aimed to create a more diverse and robust economic base.

However, it is important to note that Indonesia has not yet fully escaped MIT. Despite significant progress, major challenges remain. Social and economic disparities continue to be barriers, and structural economic transformation has not yet been fully realized. The expected snowball effect that could accelerate progress still requires time to yield optimal results. Therefore, although Jokowi's policy direction and strategies are on the right track, more consistent and sustained efforts are needed to ensure that Indonesia can surpass the MIT and achieve more inclusive and sustainable economic growth in the future.

Looking to the future, the vision of Indonesia Emas 2045, in which Indonesia aims to achieve advanced nation status by its centenary, serves as a guiding light. Escaping MIT is a critical milestone in this journey, as breaking free from MIT is essential for realizing the ambitions of Indonesia Emas 2045. Through appropriate policies and effective implementation, the dream of becoming an advanced nation is not merely a fantasy but a reachable goal. The successful realization of Indonesia Emas 2045 will not only reflect the effectiveness of government policies but also symbolize the collective determination of the Indonesian people to secure a brighter and greater future.

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